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The Effect of Tax Education on Tax Awareness: An Experimental Research in Diyarbakır Province¹

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Abstract

This study used experimental methods to create intervention and control groups in order to examine the impact of tax education on tax awareness, based on the hypothesis that tax awareness can be learned at a young age. The Ministry of National Education and the Provincial Directorates of National Education gave their assent for the research, which was conducted at four pilot schools chosen in Diyarbakır. Prior to and following the 2-month tax awareness training, a survey was administered in a few chosen schools, and the findings were analysed using the SPSS programme. It is determined from the results that tax awareness education significantly raises children's tax awareness levels. After receiving tax awareness training, it was determined that children's views on taxes had changed, and they were more aware of the reason behind tax collection. Within the context of the study's findings, policy recommendations were made.

Key Words: Tax Awareness, Tax Education, Primary School Students, SPSS Analysis

JEL Codes: H20, H29, H26

1. Introduction

The problem of tax collection is fundamentally related to tax awareness. Like all other fundamental standards, raising tax awareness is a value that should be learned early in life. Supporting it throughout the education and training process, starting with the family, will enable one to fully acquire this awareness. In Turkey, the issue of tax awareness is remembered only with some events during tax week, and tax information programs are held for students only on these days. This circumstance is insufficient to raise tax awareness, particularly among students. The aim of this study is to increase tax awareness, considering that primary school students are potential taxpayers. In this context, the tax awareness of the students who will be included in the project was measured. Then, it was aimed to increase the tax awareness levels of the students with 2-month periodic tax training. After the tax training, various activities were held with the students and the survey form applied before the training was re-applied. According to the survey findings, it was observed that there was an increase in the tax awareness levels of students.

The study consists of three parts. In the first chapter, the concept of tax awareness was examined and tax awareness in children was specifically discussed. In the second part of the

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study, the results of the survey conducted to measure and increase tax awareness in children are shared and the research method and findings are included. Policy recommendations and other findings regarding all outcomes of the study are discussed in the conclusion section.

2. Tax Awareness

Tax awareness means having understanding and knowledge about the tax system and tax laws in a country (Faizal, Zaini & Somasundaram, 2021: 66). It also includes being aware of the rules, regulations and procedures when fulfilling tax obligations. Tax awareness, in a sense, is a cognitive process about why taxes are paid and why tax regulations should be followed (Sanusi et al, 2021: 91). Buehler (1940:237) stated that tax awareness can also be defined as tax education or tax knowledge. Accordingly, tax awareness means increasing knowledge about the tax burden and its connection with public expenditures and obtaining more taxpayers. This definition actually stems from the belief that some segments of the society are not aware of the burden imposed by taxes or are partially aware of this burden (Buehler, 1940: 238).

2.1. Children and Tax Awareness

Education; It is a lifelong process that prepares society as an aspect of socialization in order to learn appropriate attitudes, values and behaviors. These norms and values may also include compliance with tax laws. "Understanding tax", which is made a part of this process, is very important in order to improve the awareness of the new generation about tax. This should be seen as a duty of states and the tax issue should be clarified in the minds of the new generation (Koster, 2012: 1-2). Lack of tax education is one of the main causes of noncompliance with tax responsibilities. Tax education initiatives that cover subjects like the economic consequences of tax evasion and the advancement of accountability and transparency have a big influence on taxpayers' voluntary compliance. Early provision of this training will influence the prospective taxpayer's perception and way of thinking in addition to increasing voluntary compliance with regard to tax payment and reporting obligations (Albert ve Fadjaranie, 2022:1913)

Countries around the world reach taxpayers through various channels to increase tax awareness. In this context, relevant institutions and organizations, especially tax administrations, are implementing programs to inform taxpayers about some tax issues and deadlines. Apart from this, initiatives such as TV programs, digital platforms, and various other mass media are also being implemented (OECD, 2021). Tax weeks (the last week of February), held every year in Turkey since 1990, are supported by tax awareness campaigns not only for children but also for all members of society. In these events, various posters are prepared for children's tax awareness and activities such as games/competitions are organized (OECD, 2021; Vergialgi, 2021; GiB, 2023d: 93-94).

3. Findings

This study was implemented in 4 public schools affiliated with the Ministry of National Education in Diyarbakır province. The group that created the scale was selected from 6th, 7th and 8th grades. A total of 427 students attended the tax training (188 female and 239 male students). Students are between the ages of 11-14. The unique and meaningful part of the study is that the survey was applied to the same 427 selected students before and after the tax awareness training. Firstly, a tax awareness survey was applied to 427 students selected in

schools, and after the survey, tax awareness training was given for 2 months. After the tax awareness training, the survey applied to the same students at the beginning of the research was repeated and the results of the experimental research were as follows.

Students were asked whether they had heard the word tax before. It was observed that there was a normal familiarity with the word tax before and after the survey. It is seen that there is an increase in the number of students who answered the question "Where did they hear the word tax" from their family before the training, and the number of students who answered the same question from their teacher after the survey. When the answers given before the survey to the question "What do you think taxes are?" were examined, it was determined that there was a significant increase in the answer "It is the money collected by the state to take care of us", while there was also an expected decrease in the answer "I don't know". It can be stated that there is an increase in tax awareness after tax training. When the answers to the question of who pays taxes are examined, it is concluded that children have the awareness that everyone who earns money must pay taxes. In addition, the decrease in the response of "I don't know" is considered as a result showing the importance of tax awareness education. When the answers to the question "why is paying taxes important" are examined, it can be stated that there is a decrease in the answers "it is not important" and "I don't know". In addition, it is observed that children who participate in tax awareness training have an awareness that taxes are important for the presentation of public goods. These results reveal that tax education is important for tax awareness. The answers given to the question "What comes to your mind when you think of taxes" before and after the tax awareness training were examined. It is observed that there has been a slight decrease in the perception of taxes only as money, as well as an increase in the perception of the concepts of schools, hospitals, parks, and security and protection when taxes are mentioned. This shows that after tax awareness training, there is an increase in tax awareness and awareness of what the main purposes of taxes are. When the answers to the question of why people pay taxes were examined, it was determined that after the tax awareness training, there was a decrease in the perception that they pay because it is compulsory, and in addition, an awareness emerged that it is a civic duty to contribute to the state.

4. Conclusion

Lack of sufficient tax awareness negatively affects tax payment and taxation processes. In connection with this, it causes tax losses and evasion to increase. This research was based on the idea that tax awareness is important in terms of tax revenues. In this context, the importance of tax awareness education is emphasized. According to the findings obtained as a result of the experimental research applied to 427 selected students in 4 schools in Diyarbakır, tax awareness education caused a significant increase in the tax awareness levels of children. It was concluded that after the tax awareness training, children's perspective on taxes changed and they became aware of the purpose for which taxes are collected. In addition, their perception of people who do not pay taxes is negative, which can be considered a positive development in terms of tax awareness. In line with the findings obtained from the study, it is recommended to add a tax awareness education course to the National Education curriculum. In addition, the Revenue Administration needs to update and diversify the content it has prepared for children.

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